

METHODS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF HEARING IN HEARING-IMPAIRED CHILDREN

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Annotation: This article talks about the methods of hearing development in hearing-impaired children, history and training.

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The method of auditory-speech and language development of deaf and hard of hearing children was developed in the 70s of the XX century. It got its name from the name of the author - Emilia Ivanovna Leonhard. Over the past decades, thousands of hearing impaired children have been trained in the Leonhard method. The stability of the results obtained in different learning conditions for children with hearing impairment and the high level of their social adaptation prove the practical effectiveness of the method.

Specialists from many countries involved in the rehabilitation of people with hearing impairments are very interested in the Russian system of E.I. Leonhard, which has recently acquired particular relevance in the light of new knowledge about the neuroplasticity of the human brain.

All achievements in the field of technical support for children with hearing impairments are effective only when they are included in the process of psychological and pedagogical habilitation or rehabilitation. By themselves, even the most advanced hearing aids and implants do not solve the problem of normalizing the auditory and language development of deaf and hard of hearing children.

There are various psychological and pedagogical systems. One of them is the System of Formation and Development of Speech Hearing and Speech Communication in Children with Hearing Impairment (Leonhard Method). It was preceded by a system of auditory education developed in the 70s by A.A. Wenger, G.L. Vygotskoy, E.I. Leonhard.

For almost 50 years, the main goal of research has been and remains the creation and improvement of the system of normalized auditory-speech and mental development of each child with hearing impairment. The basis of the methodology is the language development of children, so the main task of

habilitation or rehabilitation is to prevent the appearance of dumbness in children - a “secondary defect” (L.S. Vygotsky), or to overcome it.

Normalization of conditions occurs in the process of implementing the system of auditory education and special work on the development of speech hearing. The normal course of hearing and speech development is carried out when children are provided with: life in the family (and not in a boarding school), life in hearing, life in language, life in communication. These conditions are necessary but not sufficient. Mandatory in this case is a long-term special work on the formation of speech hearing in children. Without this, even implanted children remain deaf and dumb, as evidenced by the sad experience that we face almost daily.

The origin and development of the auditory and auditory-speech systems occurs due to the functioning of the mechanism of speech hearing. This is a stable structure consisting of 4 elements: reception of a speech signal - its almost synchronous oral reproduction - synchronous self-listening - comprehension of what is heard and spoken.

However, one can speak about the formation of speech hearing only when all the elements of the structure are functioning, and especially the fourth element. If the child only repeats what he hears, but does not understand the meaning of the word or the meaning of the statement, then we are not dealing with speech hearing, but with the auditory function (heard - repeated, but did not comprehend).

The ability to hear first of all means the ability to understand. Therefore, the material of special classes for the development of speech hearing is only meaningful units of speech: words, phrases, phrases, texts. Training in the perception of isolated sounds is necessary when setting up the implant mode, but, in accordance with our concept, sounds cannot be the material of classes for the development of speech hearing. First, sound is not a carrier of meaning. Secondly, in combination with other sounds, it is perceived differently than in an isolated form. Thirdly, if you specifically teach children to hear all the sounds in a word, they will not be able to catch the meaning of the word, because they will be focused on its analysis. (We are now seeing such a picture in one implanted student of the GUIMC MSTU named after Bauman, who does not yet hear all the sounds in words and therefore refuses to correlate what he hears with the objects they designate).

The development of the auditory-speech system occurs in accordance with the patterns of development of oral speech of hearing children. Just like hearing people, deaf people with hearing aids or implants initially perceive speech by

ear as a whole, globally, and they are not forced to immediately reproduce all sounds in words. Children correlate what they hear with an object, a toy, an action. What they hear is interesting to them, filled with content. As with hearing people, in children with hearing impairment, the sound analysis of words is formed gradually, as a result of speech material specially selected for classes. In a rather amorphous structure of the sound complex at the beginning of habilitation, the hearing impaired in the process of studying and living in their hearing begin to hear individual elements characteristic of a given word: combinations of two or three sounds, syllables, and even individual sounds. Of course, well-prosthetic hearing-impaired children and former deaf children after cochlear implantation reach this level faster. But the patterns of this path are common to all.

The formation of the auditory-speech system of people with hearing impairment is complete when this process includes teaching literacy - reading and writing. This work is best started at an early preschool age. Here, too, the focus is on the meaning, that is, the word, acquaintance with individual letters and reading meaningless syllables is excluded.

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